

FLUORESCENCE POLARIZATION IMAGING FOR THE QUANTITATIVE DETECTION OF RENAL CANCER BIOMARKERS

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to investigate multimodal confocal imaging of Methylene Blue (MB) stained cancerous and normal human renal cells. Our polarization enhanced imaging system provided reflectance and fluorescence emission images for assessing cellular morphology, along with quantitative Fluorescence Polarization (Fpol) images. This combined fluorescence emission/Fpol approach offers key advantages over traditional cytopathological methods for analyzing renal Fine- Needle Aspiration (FNA) biopsies.

FNA specimens were collected from malignant and benign renal masses following surgery at Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Center, Boston, US. Samples were stained with MB prior to multimodal confocal imaging. Our findings show that Fpol values of cancerous renal cells were significantly higher than those of benign cells. These Fpol signatures served as a reliable quantitative metric for detecting cancer at the single-cell level. Moreover, imaging results closely matched the clinical cytopathology diagnoses. Overall, these findings indicate that the quantitative information provided by Fpol imaging may be valuable for determining the presence or absence of renal cancer cells in FNA specimens.

INTRODUCTION

In the past five years, the global burden of renal cancer has continued to rise, with annual incidence now exceeding 430,000 cases and mortality approaching 160,000 deaths worldwide [1]. In the United States, kidney cancer remains a significant public-health concern, with nearly 81,000 new cases and around 14,000 deaths reported each year [2]. Although Pakistan lacks a comprehensive national cancer registry, regional data suggest a steady increase in

renal cell carcinoma, reflecting a growing disease burden across South Asia [3, 4].

Fluorescence polarization (Fpol) imaging of methylene blue (MB) is a promising quantitative approach to cancer detection [5]. The fluorescence polarization (Fpol) of Methylene Blue (MB) is significantly higher in cancer than in normal human breast tissues and cells [6]. Evaluation and statistical analysis of MB fluorescence polarization values

The illustration depicts the major optical and scanning components of the system, including the diode laser source (1), beam splitters (2), dichroic mirror (3), scanning mirrors (10–12), microscope optics (4–5), emission detection pathway (6–8), sample stage (13), and data acquisition unit (14). The configuration demonstrates the flow of excitation light to the sample and the subsequent collection and detection of emitted fluorescence.

The detection pathway included 100- μm pinholes, after which the fluorescence signal was directed toward the detectors by a dichroic mirror (Iridian, Ottawa, Canada) and filtered through a bandpass filter (Thorlabs, Inc., Newton, New Jersey) centered at 690 nm (FWHM = 20 nm). The emitted light was divided into co-polarized and cross-polarized channels using a polarizing beam splitter (Karl Lambrecht Co., Chicago, Illinois). Elastically scattered light was transmitted through the dichroic mirror and then reflected by a nonpolarizing beam splitter mirror (Edmund Optics, Barrington, New Jersey) into a PMT. For imaging, a 60 \times NA1.2 water-immersion objective lens (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan) was used, providing a 250- μm field of view. The polygon scanner (Lincoln Laser, Phoenix, Arizona) enabled a lateral resolution of 0.8 μm , axial resolution of 2.7

μm , and an imaging rate of nine frames per second. System control and synchronization were performed via the VivaScan controller (Caliber I.D., Andover, Massachusetts).

Image Processing

8-bit grayscale co- and cross-polarized fluorescence images captured by the system were inserted into Equation 1, yielding the quantitative Fpol image:

$$F_{\text{pol}} = \frac{I_{\parallel} - G \times I_{\perp}}{I_{\parallel} + G \times I_{\perp}} \quad (1)$$

Here I_{\parallel} is the co-polarized fluorescence intensity registered by channel 1 of the imaging system and I_{\perp} is the cross-polarized fluorescence intensity registered by channel 2. The coefficient G is a calibration factor that offsets different efficiencies exhibited by channels 1 and 2 for detecting co- polarized versus cross-polarized components of the fluorescent light. To determine G , the protocol

described by Seigel [21] was used in which Fpol measurements from the imaging system were compared to Fpol measurements of the same homogenous solution performed using a fluorometer (Horiba, Edison, NJ). For these experiments, the calibration factor was determined to be $G = 0.80$ [16]. Quantitative grayscale Fpol images were processed and assigned pseudo-color using ImageJ, which is available from the National Institutes of Health. Fpol image analysis was performed using MetaMorph software (Molecular Devices, Sunnyvale, CA). An inclusive threshold was applied to exclude background noise (pixel value < 2) and saturated pixels (pixel value > 254). Renal cells were segmented and the average intensity and standard deviation of each cell was calculated. For each sample, cells were grouped according to size and the average MB Fpol for each group was determined.

Results and Discussion

We present the results obtained from imaging four renal FNAs, including two diagnosed as renal cell carcinoma (samples 1 and 2) and two as normal specimens (samples 3 and 4). Reflectance, fluorescence emission and Fpol images were acquired, and the number of cells present in each sample was established. Samples 1 and 2 both contained 63 cells, while samples 3 and 4 contained 53 and 34 cells, respectively. In total, we have quantitatively analyzed 213 renal cells from all the specimens. Along with cell count, the mean diameter of each cell was determined from the images. All samples were found to be heterogeneous, including various cell sizes ranging in diameter from < 11 μm to > 20 μm . For each sample, cells were categorized by their size into a small (< 11 μm), medium (11-20 μm), or large (> 20 μm) group. Experimental data from each sample is summarized in Table 1. From the cancerous specimens, 126 cells were examined. Sample 1 contained 2 small cells, 30 medium cells and 31 large cells exhibiting averaged Fpol values of 0.230 ± 0.011 , 0.241 ± 0.025 , and 0.260 ± 0.019 , respectively. In sample 1, average cell size ranged from $10.37 \pm 0.53 \mu\text{m}$ in the small category to $29.93 \pm 6.80 \mu\text{m}$ in the large category. Sample 2 contained 21 small cells, 24 medium cells, and 18 large cells with averaged Fpol values of 0.221 ± 0.023 , 0.251 ± 0.022 , and 0.247 ± 0.015 , respectively. For the second malignant sample,

average cell size ranged from $9.65 \pm 1.26 \mu\text{m}$ (small group) to $24.33 \pm 2.98 \mu\text{m}$ (large group). The two normal samples contained 87 total cells for analysis. Sample 3 included 43 small cells and 10 medium cells with averaged Fpol values of 0.224 ± 0.018 and 0.214 ± 0.21 , respectively. Sample 4 included 27 small cells and 7 medium cells with respective averaged Fpol

values of 0.212 ± 0.025 and 0.221 ± 0.039 . Both normal samples did not include large cells greater than $20 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter. For sample 3, average size ranged from $8.95 \pm 0.90 \mu\text{m}$ (small group) to $11.83 \pm 1.49 \mu\text{m}$ (medium group), while in sample 4 average sizes were $8.50 \pm 1.22 \mu\text{m}$ (small group) to $13.07 \pm 3.06 \mu\text{m}$ (medium group).

Table 1. Summary of the Experimental Data.

Sample I.D.	Cell Group Small (< 11 μm) Medium (11-20 μm) Large (> 20 μm)	No. of Cells	Averaged Cell [μm]	Averaged Fpol	Diagnosis
1 (n = 63)	Small	2	10.37 ± 0.53	0.230 ± 0.011	clear cell RCC with tubulopapillary RCC
	Medium	30	14.54 ± 2.26	0.241 ± 0.025	
	Large	31	29.93 ± 6.80	0.260 ± 0.019	
2 (n = 63)	Small	21	9.65 ± 1.26	0.221 ± 0.023	clear cell RCC with tubulopapillary RCC
	Medium	24	16.78 ± 2.84	0.251 ± 0.022	
	Large	18	24.33 ± 2.98	0.247 ± 0.015	
3 (n = 53)	Small	43	8.95 ± 0.90	0.224 ± 0.018	normal
	Medium	10	11.83 ± 1.49	0.214 ± 0.21	
	Large	0	N/A	N/A	
4 (n = 34)	Small	27	8.50 ± 1.22	0.212 ± 0.025	normal
	Medium	7	13.07 ± 3.06	0.221 ± 0.039	
	Large	0	N/A	N/A	

Clinical diagnosis of the samples was obtained from BIDMC and compared with outcomes of the optical imaging. Samples 1 and 2 were cancerous, and were diagnosed as clear cell RCC with tubulopapillary RCC. Samples 3 and 4 were diagnosed as normal renal specimens. The majority of cells found in the

cancerous FNAs were medium or large sized. Sample 1 contained 48% medium sized and 49% large sized cells, whereas sample 2 contained 38% medium and 29% large sized cells. This is in contrast to the FNAs acquired from normal kidney tissue, which primarily included small cells. Samples 3 and 4 were made up of 81%

and 79% small cells, respectively. Quantitative analysis of the data shows the most significant differences in MB Fpol occur between medium sized cells in the cancerous and normal samples, while the smallest Fpol differences were observed between small cells in the samples. The highest Fpol measurements recorded occurred in large cells

present in samples 1 and 2, the two specimens known to contain renal cell carcinoma. The absence of large cells in samples 3 and 4 precluded direct comparison of Fpol measurements made for this group between normal and malignant specimens. Figure 3.

Figure 2 a) Papillary RCC (low grade), b) Papillary RCC (low grade), Chromophobe RCC, c) normal renal tubular cells d) Normal renal tubular cells

Figure 4 shows a histogram of MB Fpol values versus cell group size for each sample 1-4. Parts A and B of the diagram display results for samples 1 and 2 that suggest increased average cell size in cancerous FNAs correlates with increased average magnitude of the Fpol signal. Parts C-D show

results for the normal specimens. Figure 4 provides a display of MB Fpol values for the medium sized cells in each of the samples 1-4. From this chart, it is evident the cancerous specimens (1 and 2) yielded higher average Fpol from cells in the size range 11-20 μm .

Figure 3. Average MB Fpol of 4 renal FNA samples. Sample 1 (A) and 2 (B), acquired from cancerous renal masses, contained small, medium and large sized cells (colored red). Samples 3 (C) and 4 (D) were acquired from normal renal tissue.

Figure 4. Average MB Fpol of samples 1-4 for the medium size range. Samples 1 and 2 were acquired from cancerous renal masses, samples 3 and 4 were acquired from normal renal tissue.

Example MB fluorescence emission and pseudo-colored quantitative Fpol images are contained in Figure 4. Figure 4A and 4B display a representative

fluorescence emission and corresponding fluorescence polarization image from sample 1, which contained cancerous renal cells. Figure 4C and

4D show a fluorescence emission and fluorescence polarization image from sample 3, which contained normal cells. The fluorescence polarization scale is located to the right in the figure, with values ranging RCC, including oval, eccentric nucleus and prominent nucleoli [15]. Cells exhibited in Figure 4C show features, including round nucleus, that are commonly described in normal renal cells[14]. The Fpol images demonstrate that cancerous renal cells

from Fpol = 0.10 (black) to Fpol = 0.34 (red). The fluorescence emission image (Figure 4A) displays cytologic features consistent with the diagnosis of clear cell (Figure 4B) exhibit higher Fpol as compared to normal renal cells (Figure 4D). The normal cells are colored blue and green, while the cancerous cells are colored yellow, red, and orange.

Figure 5 (A) Example fluorescence emission image of clear cell RCC present in sample 1. (B) Corresponding pseudo-colored Fpol image of cancerous cells. (C) Fluorescence emission image of normal renal cells present in sample 3. (D) Pseudo-colored Fpol image of normal cells. Bar = 50 μm .

We tested the hypothesis that Fpol of medium sized cells averaged over both cancerous samples (1 and 2) was greater than that from medium sized cells averaged over both normal samples (3 and 4). We determined the average pixel value corresponding to Fpol for medium sized cells in samples 1-2 was 0.245 ± 0.011 , similarly for samples 3-4 the average Fpol was

0.216 ± 0.010 . The statistical significance of this difference in Fpol was evaluated by employing a one-tailed Student's *t*-test for 2 independent populations. A highly significant difference ($p < 0.0001$) was observed in MB Fpol of medium sized cells in the cancerous versus normal FNAs. Further analysis demonstrates

average Fpol of cells in the cancerous samples was 13% higher than that of cells in the normal samples, for the medium size range.

To verify that our measurements of Fpol signal originate from living cells, we conducted a Trypan blue exclusion test on each sample following the

optical imaging. Viable cells, already stained with MB reject the Trypan blue dye, whereas nonviable cells uptake the dye and thus appear purple in color. We found that nearly all the cells remained viable after the experiments.

Figure 6. Bright-field images of live and dead cells following Trypan Blue staining. The red arrows point to living cells (blue) stained with MB. The black arrows point to dead cells (purple) stained with MB and Trypan Blue. Bar = 100 μm .

Conclusion

In this observational study, we have presented the first results from measuring quantitative Fpol signature of single cells. Multi-modal confocal imaging of renal FNA specimens permitted qualitative examination of the cells along with quantifiable Fpol measurements. Results from imaging were consistent with the clinical diagnosis. This report details preliminary observations and no broad conclusions can be drawn. Future works will focus on statistically significant evaluations of this method for measuring *in vitro* and *in vivo* Fpol in various types of cells.

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